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Letter to the Editor: The Case against Mandatory Covid Vaccination in Nigeria

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Introduction

Outbreaks The Nigerian COVID Response Alliance is a wholly-indigenous movement formed to monitor the official response to the COVID-19 pandemic in Nigeria; and ensure that the response remains within the ambit of reason, and citizens' fundamental human rights. We have [previously](#) clarified [NCRA 2021] that our grouse is not with vaccines themselves, but their being blindly mandated for everybody without due comprehensive and holistic risk-benefit considerations for both individuals and society as a whole. In June 2020, we saw in the proposed amendment to the Control of Infectious Diseases Act, a dastardly attempt to foist mandatory vaccination on Nigerians with grim implications both for basic freedom and public health. We also foresaw a more grievous scenario following, as nanobots, already developed but currently held in abeyance, are unceremoniously deployed once mandatory vaccination has been established and accepted. To forestall all these, we consequently submitted a Memorandum [NCRA 2020] to the House of Representatives during the public hearing on the Bill.

The unjustifiable (in our opinion) mandating of COVID vaccination which began surreptitiously at the 20th National Sports Festival [[Edo 2021](#)] subsequently reached all employees of the Federal Government, cascaded to members of the National Youth Service Corp scheme [Guardian 2021], and is currently indirectly threatening young school leavers with the announcements by the Joint Admissions Matriculation Board [[JAMB 2021](#)] that the mandates will be enforced at her facilities as fully as possible. The heat is also being put on employees at the [Local Government](#) levels [Punch 2021]; and indications have emerged of government attempting to conflate COVID and childhood vaccines which could potentially see day-olds (presumably "accidentally") receiving COVID vaccines! [[Independent 2021](#)].

In this submission, we highlight some cogent points why the idea of mandatory COVID vaccination should not be entertained in Nigeria. A detailed presentation together with more extensive references can be found at our archive [NCRA 2022].

Summary of the Case against Mandatory COVID vaccination in Nigeria

1. The Vaccines being mandated in Nigeria are all experimental and have not been *approved* for regular use by any scientific or medical authority. All they have is Emergency Use *Authorization*. Furthermore in a demonstration of an incredible level of audacious opacity, details of the actual contents of the vaccines, together with the Contracts with the pharmaceutical companies for their acquisition, are shrouded in utter secrecy. Not only ethics, but local and international laws demand that such products be not mandated [NPBR 2018, StatNews 2021].

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2. Furthermore, even for approved medical products, it is expected that would-be recipients would be adequately informed by the prescribing physicians, of both benefits and risks associated with the product. The contraindications should be made clear, and alternatives should be presented and made available. Mandatory vaccination, and that of an unapproved product in particular, flagrantly violates these sacrosanct norms of modern science. Indeed, the [Fact Sheets](#) for the COVID vaccines specifically require that would-be recipients be informed of some vaccine contents, such as polyethylene glycol (PEG), which could be fatal to people allergic to it. [e.g. Moderna 2022]. The simple fact is that most Nigerians are not even aware of their allergy status with respect to such chemicals! The presumed “consent” of Nigerians who receive these vaccines is therefore certainly far from being “informed”.

3. The Vaccines are demonstrably NOT efficacious. Hence the need for unending “booster” doses, while the “fully vaccinated” must continue to observe same protocols as they were before the jab. New virus variants are known to evolve in response to mass vaccination, and are not by any means attributable to the unvaccinated population as is being suggested in certain quarters. There is no country/territory anywhere that has overcome COVID-19 via vaccines. On the other hand, a country like [Gibraltar](#) with 100% vaccination rate continues to witness the highest severity level of COVID 19, while countries/territories that changed course from sole-dependence on mass vaccination to embrace other alternatives (like [Croatia](#), [Denmark](#), [Norway](#), [Japan](#), the Provinces of [Uttar Pradesh](#) and [Delhi](#) in India, and [a number of states](#) in the US) are all witnessing dramatic improvement in their COVID situations – often within weeks of such decisions! The [UK](#), [Czech Republic](#), [Netherlands](#), and [Ireland](#) are the latest countries to join the wagon of those dropping the clearly unprofitable vaccine mandate. [Specific references to the countries listed above can be found in reference NCRA 2022].

4. The Vaccines have been conclusively proven to be NOT safe. Not only are the scientific basis for numerous adverse effects now well established and published in reputable scientific and medical journals, the existence of such adverse effects are already being adequately demonstrated from public health data available globally. Such effects include acute ones such as myocarditis, blood clotting, and death, as well as longer-term ones including adverse reproductive outcomes and [Cancers](#). [Natural News 2021, Fraiman et al 2022].

5. The financial costs of the COVID vaccines are unjustified, especially in the face of other more compelling public health challenges Nigeria uniquely faces. Credit facilities offered us to facilitate our response to COVID (largely procurement, storage, and deployment of COVID vaccines) are now well [in excess of 3 billion dollars](#), far exceeding our total [annual health budget](#) [Nairametrics 2020, PremiumTimes 2021].

6. The value of natural immunity is significant and cannot be discountenanced as is being attempted by the vaccine pushers. It is now well-established that naturally-acquired immunity against COVID-19 is far [superior](#) to vaccine-acquired immunity – in terms of [efficacy](#), [robustness](#) and [duration](#) [Gazit et al 2021]. As has been established in the case of measles and smallpox for example, people who have recovered from COVID-19 and have consequently acquired natural immunity should not be required to receive a COVID jab again.

7. Other proven solutions exist for COVID-19, despite amazing desperate efforts to demonize and proscribe these alternatives. Articles published in the world’s topmost medical journals to push such conspiracy have been [later shown](#) to be pure forgery and unceremoniously retracted. [[Piller](#) and [Servick](#) 2020]. Nevertheless policy decisions taken on the strength of these fake scientific data continue to be unabashedly used to push mandatory vaccination and associated measures.

Conclusion

Not only are the supposed benefits of the COVID vaccine vague, the costs in various dimensions are steep and unacceptable. Patriotic Nigerians must rise to help extricate our Government from the manipulative clutches of foreign and private interests who are the barely-hidden forces behind these mandates. system.

References

- Edo 2021. <https://www.insidethegames.biz/articles/1106028/covid-vaccine-mandatory-nigeria-event>.
- Fraiman J, Erviti J, Jones M, Greenland S, Whelan P, Kaplan RM, Doshi P. Serious adverse events of special interest following mRNA COVID-19 vaccination in randomized trials in adults. *Vaccine*. 2022 Sep 22;40(40):5798-5805. doi: 10.1016/j.vaccine.2022.08.036. Epub 2022 Aug 31. PMID: 36055877; PMCID: PMC9428332.
- Gazit, Sivan; Rои Shlezinger, Galit Perez, Roni Lotan, Asaf Peretz, Amir Ben-Tov, Dani Cohen, Khitam Muhsen, Gabriel Chodick, Tal Patalon. Comparing SARS-CoV-2 natural immunity to vaccine-induced immunity: reinfections versus breakthrough infections. medRxiv 2021.08.24.21262415; doi: <https://doi.org/10.1101/2021.08.24.21262415>. Now published in *Clinical Infectious Diseases* doi: [10.1093/cid/ciac262](https://doi.org/10.1093/cid/ciac262)
- Guardian 2021. <https://guardian.ng/news/nysc-goes-stringent-on-covid-19-protocols-as-2021-batch-c-stream-ii-service-year-begins/>
- Independent 2021. <https://independent.ng/nigeria-to-integrate-childhood-immunisation-into-covid-19-vaccination-nphcda/>
- JAMB 2021. https://punchng.com/jamb-makes-vaccination-compulsory-for-workers-visitors/?utm_source=auto-read-also&utm_medium=web
- Moderna 2022. Vaccine Fact Sheets: <https://www.modernatx.com/covid19vaccine-eua/eua-fact-sheet-recipients.pdf> (revised June 17, 2022).
- Nairametrics2020. <https://nairametrics.com/2020/12/22/fg-plans-to-purchase-vaccines-for-n400-billion-health-minister/>
- Natural News 2021. <https://www.naturalnews.com/2021-11-02-science-horror-vaccine-spike-protein-enters-cell-nuclei-suppresses-dna-repair-engine-of-the-human-body-cancer-aging.html>
- NCRA 2020: Memorandum to the Public Hearing on the Control of Infectious Diseases Bill 2020 (HB. 836). <http://blog.lsfnigeria.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/SUBMISSION-TO-THE-JUNE-2020-PUBLIC-HEARING-AT-THE-HOUSE-OF-REPRESENTATIVES-.pdf>
- NCRA 2021. Press Statement. <https://covidvaccineunmasked.com/blog/press-statement-ncra-30th-august-2021>
- NCRA 2022. The Case against Mandatory COVID Vaccination in Nigeria. A Position Paper by the Nigerian COVID Response Alliance. [https://covidvaccineunmasked.com/images/docs/Position_Paper_NCRA. - Final Version.pdf](https://covidvaccineunmasked.com/images/docs/Position_Paper_NCRA_-_Final_Version.pdf).
- NPBR 2018. Nigeria Patients Bill of Rights. <https://www.fccpc.gov.ng/uploads/files/patients-bill-of-rights-full-version.pdf>.
- Piller, Charles and Servick, Kelly 2020. Two elite medical journals retract coronavirus papers over data integrity questions. <https://www.science.org/content/article/two-elite-medical-journals-retract-coronavirus-papers-over-data-integrity-questions>. June 4 2020.
- PremiumTimes 2021. <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/news/headlines/421129-2021-budget-again-nigeria-ignores-au-benchmark-for-health-funding.html>
- Punch 2021. <https://punchng.com/enforce-compulsory-vaccination-for-lg-state-workers-fg-tells-govs/>
- StatNews 2021: <https://www.statnews.com/2021/02/23/federal-law-prohibits-employers-and-others-from-requiring-vaccination-with-a-covid-19-vaccine-distributed-under-an-eua/>